

PAIN MANAGEMENT AND ASSESSMENT IN POST OPERATIVE PATIENTS: A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Human beings have witnessed numerous sensory phenomena. Pain is a vital component among us, although its basis is entirely subjective. Different people felt pain in different ways. Based mostly on their frequency of occurrence, pain was classified as either acute or chronic. Pain has an effect on people's socioeconomic standing. Standard SCALES were used to assess pain in a variety of ways. Methods: This was a multicenter, prospective observational research. Findings: The current investigation was conducted in several hospitals in the Bathinda region between August 2022 and December 2023. Of the 775 patients who took part in the current investigation, 290 were male and the remainder were female. According to the 4-hour VAS evaluation, 39.32% of people reported having moderate pain, and 19.75% reported having severe pain.

Key words: Sensory phenomena, Moderate pain, VAS evaluation, Chronic and Acute pain.

INTRODUCTION:

Described in terms of actual or potential tissue damage, pain is defined as an individual's subjective, unpleasant feeling or discomfort. It is a personal, subjective experience influenced by social, psychological, and physical factors. There are no reliable methods for measuring pain^(1,2).

There are two categories of pain: acute and chronic. Scales for measuring pain were essential in the post-operative care of patients.

The different types of scales are as follows⁽³⁾

a) Facial scale
b) Numerical rating scale
c) FLACC scale
d) CRISE scale
e) COMFORT scale
f) Mc Gill Pain scale
g) Color Analog scale
h) Mankoski pain scale
i) Brief pain Inventory
j) Visual Analog scale

The following information should be included in the pain history ^(4,5):

- Notable past and/or current episodes of pain and how they have affected the patient
- Comments regarding the techniques employed in the past to lessen the indicated discomfort.
- Drugs that cause habit formation, such as hypnotics, sedatives, and opioids, have a notable impact on people's behavior.
- Support from family members and opinions on how to manage pain after surgery, including whether therapy was successful or not.
- Compliant patients.

RESOURCES AND TECHNIQUES

Study design:

From August 2022 to December 2023, the current study was conducted at several hospitals in the Bathinda district of India. Every patient who had any kind of operation was registered. Clinical information was gathered. Evaluation is done on pain assessment and treatment.

Objectives:

Estimating pain assessment and control in patients who have had post-operative surgery is our main objective.

Study Method:

This multicenter, prospective observational study was conducted. The patient case sheet provided the patient's details, and the necessary information was typed into data gathering forms. The information was grouped according to a number of criteria, including gender, age, co-morbidities, prescribed medications, and post-operative pain assessment. Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) (5) was used to assess pain.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who are older than eighteen years
- Individuals who voluntarily participate without coercion or evidence of benefit

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients under the age of eighteen and those receiving ICU treatment

Data and statistics:

SPSS software was used to analyze the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The current investigation involved 775 patients in all. There were 417 men and 358 women among them. In Table 1, Figure 1, the gender distribution of the study participants was displayed.

Table 1: Gender Distribution

	Number	Percentage
Women	358	46.2
Men	417	53.8
Total	775	

Figure 1: Gender Distribution

Table 2: Number of

Patients undergone the various kind of surgeries

Type of Ward	No. of patients	%
Thoracic surgery	130	16.77
Gynecology	145	18.71
Orthopedics	180	23.23
Laryngology	30	3.87
Neurosurgery	35	4.52
Urology	30	3.87
Obstetrics	45	5.81
General Surgery	158	20.39
Vascular Surgery	22	2.84
Total	775	100

Figure 2: Distribution of Patients as per kind of surgery

The data for the study was collected from the many hospitals in the Bathinda Region of Punjab, India, throughout that period. Table 2 and Figure 2 both provided an overview of the different types of surgeries, the number of patients, and the proportion of surgeries. The data revealed that vascular surgery had a low occupancy of 22 out of 775, whereas orthopedic surgeries accounted for the majority of the list with 180 out of 775.

After surgery, the VAS was used to analyze the degree of pain for up to 24 hours, adhering to a predetermined schedule of 4, 8, 12, and 24 hours. Table 3 displayed the pain intensity values, while Figure 3 provided a graphic representation of the same data. Based on the VAS for Moderate and Severe pain following surgery, the results were discussed.

Table 3: Patient pain intensity expressed by using VAS after surgery

VAS (h)	Mean	Moderate Pain		Severe Pain	
		Number	%	Number	%
4	34.05	305	39.32	153	19.75
8	32.07	258	33.27	112	14.41
12	27.1	186	24.02	92	11.92
24	25.08	160	20.64	66	8.54

Figure 3: Patient Pain intensity as per VAS

Post-operative analgesics were administered to the patients in accordance with their needs and rationale. A few patients had their postoperative pain situations treated with no analgesics at all. Table 4 contains information about the analgesics prescribed for pain following surgery. Moreover, Figure 4 illustrated the same concept.

Figure 4: Distribution of Analgesics used in postoperative pain,

Table 4: Analgesics used in postoperative pain

Name of the Drug	Number
No Analgesic	52
Aspirin	3
Bupivacaine+ Fentanyl	47
Diclofenac	54
Gabapentin	3
Ibuprofen	3
Ketoprofen	275
Lignocaine	6
Mefenamic Acid	3
Metamizol	482
Morphine	40
Nalbuphine	3
Paracetamol	248
Tramadol	262

Table 5: Number and Percentage of anesthesia in various categories performed

Type	No. of patients	Percent age
General	425	54.84
Subarachnoid	162	20.90
Epidural	57	7.35
Peripheral Regional	52	6.71
Combined (Spinal&Epidural)	6	0.77
General+epidural	19	2.45
General+peripheral	45	5.81
Subarachnoid+ peripheral	9	1.16

The patients were administered different anesthetics according to their requirements and the underlying reasoning. Table 5 lists the number and percentage of patients who received anesthesia in different categories. This information is also visually depicted in Figure 5.

CONCLUSION:

According to recent findings, a significant number of patients experience moderate or severe pain in the postoperative period, despite existing standard treatment guidelines aimed at effectively managing postoperative pain. In some individuals, analgesics may not provide adequate relief. The study suggests that the type of medical department, occupation, and genetic factors may influence the severity of postoperative pain.

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